

DEVELOPMENT OF LEARNING AND COGNITIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS AS A FACTOR OF INCREASING THEIR FURTHER SOCIAL COMPETITIVENESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13269038>

Abstract: The article raises the problem of increasing the level of reading literacy of pupils through increasing the level of formation of their skills in working with information. Russian comprehensive program aimed at the formation and development of educational and cognitive competence of schoolchildren can become a mechanism for solving this problem. The practical aspect of the article is a description of international experience in the formation of educational and cognitive competence of students through project assignments, successfully implemented in schools in Latvia.

Key words: educational and cognitive competence, assessment criteria, reading literacy.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the context of global technology development, intensive modernization of socio-economic processes, and a high level of uncertainty, the key intangible factor in the region's progress is the quality of human capital.

According to a study conducted by the Higher School of Economics, currently the leaders in the world have become countries that "have learned better than others to form and use the knowledge, skills, competencies of people, their ability for further learning and complexly organized joint activities" [3]. Thus, nowadays education plays a huge role in achieving success both for an individual and for an entire country. If people receive quality education, this leads to the development of science and technology, and therefore to the economic growth of the state.

At the same time, as noted by S.G. Thieves, Russian schoolchildren's performance in reading literacy, for example, has long been a cause for concern. This was due to both low quantitative indicators and their negative dynamics. According to a 2006 PISA study, 64.3% of 15-year-old students in Russia had the literate reading skills necessary for adaptation in society. A high level of reading literacy, consisting in the ability to understand complex texts, critically evaluate the information provided, formulate hypotheses and conclusions, was demonstrated by only 1.7% of Russian students [1].

2 TECHNOLOGY FOR OBTAINING MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHOD

Most international experts diagnosed not so much the presence of a low level of development of reading skills, but rather a low level of development of schoolchildren's ability to work with information.

The solution to this problem should have been a targeted comprehensive program covering all aspects of students' educational activities, all academic subjects and all stages of schooling [1].

This program was based on a model of the content of educational and cognitive competence of schoolchildren, which has the following structure:

- 1) the range of objects of reality and knowledge, in relation to which educational and cognitive competence is introduced;
- 2) social and personal significance of educational and cognitive competence;
- 3) the body of knowledge about the system of objects of reality and knowledge, in relation to which educational and cognitive competence is based;
- 4) a set of skills and abilities included in the educational and cognitive competence [1].

In general, educational-educational-cognitive competence is considered as "a requirement for students to master a complex procedure that integrates a set of interrelated semantic orientations, knowledge and skills that allow them to carry out self-managed activities to solve real cognitive problems, accompanied by the mastery of the knowledge and skills necessary to resolve them in obtaining and processing and application of information" [1]. By competence, methodological scientists proposed to understand "the student's possession of the relevant competence, including his personal attitude towards it and the subject of activity" [2]. Thus, educational-cognitive competence determines the content of educational-cognitive competence that the student needs to master.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND THEIR DISCUSSION

One of the means of developing educational and cognitive competence is the organization of project work for students. In the course of teaching the Russian language in Latvian schools, in accordance with approved programs, schoolchildren are offered various project tasks, for example, screening Russian films on a certain topic, preparing a presentation in the format of a film review [4].

By reading professional reviews, the student broadens his horizons and acquires the ability to critically perceive and speak analytically about films and videos in Russian, and provide a review of a film or production he has seen.

The list of tasks looks like this:

1. Find reviews of a movie you watched.

2. Discuss the content and form, author and source of reviews.
3. Compare the style and language of reviews.
4. Create a recall plan.
5. Write your review (500-600 words).
6. Compare your review with the reviews of your classmates, give recommendations to your classmates.
7. Improve and publish your review.

The following are assessment criteria for each stage of educational and cognitive activity of students.

Criterion "Knowledge and understanding".

High level: the review fully reveals the understanding of the film: the time and location of the plot, the peculiarities of the acting, the specifics of the work of the director and cameraman, the role of the film in the historical and social context, as well as personal recommendations for new viewers.

Medium level: the review almost completely reveals an understanding of the film: the time and location of the plot, the peculiarities of the acting, the specifics of the work of the director and cameraman, the role of the film in the historical and social context, as well as personal recommendations for new viewers.

Low level: the review partially reveals an understanding of the film: the time and location of the plot, the peculiarities of the acting, the specifics of the work of the director and cameraman, the role of the film in the historical and social context, as well as personal recommendations for new viewers.

Unacceptable Level: The review does not convey an understanding of the film.

Criterion "Text literacy".

High level: the structure of the review is clear, the parts are logically coordinated, the textual content is revealed. The review expresses the author's vision in the author's characteristic style and is supported by arguments, relevant quotes from the film and/or from other reviews, and logical conclusions are drawn.

Criterion "Use of language".

High level: the language used in the review is grammatically diverse, some vocabulary, spelling, punctuation and grammatical inaccuracies do not interfere with perceiving and understanding the author's opinion. The vocabulary used in the review is varied, includes idiomatic expressions, the choice of words is correct, and the author's style corresponds to the journalistic style.

CONCLUSIONS.

Particular attention should be paid to the pedagogical cooperation between the teacher and students, during which conditions are created for the implementation of project tasks. Students' positive attitude towards the proposed tasks is formed by creating an atmosphere of cooperation based on friendliness and support. An atmosphere of mutual respect, exactingness and trust increases students' motivation, gives them confidence in their abilities and faith in success. With this approach to the educational process, all its subjects receive support, since project tasks are carried out through business and friendly

communication with full mutual understanding and mutual assistance.

Thus, we can consider educational and cognitive competence as a factor in the social competitiveness of students, since it not only allows them to receive a high-quality general education, but also develops skills in project activities, self-study, creative and communication abilities, allowing school graduates to organically integrate into the system of lifelong learning. education on the path to a better version of yourself.

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